

The Mediating Role Of Employee Engagement Between Talent Management Practices And Organizational Commitment

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Abstract

This examination was done in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan Private Banking Sector utilizing cross-sectional, quantitative research design plan & survey research methodology. The direct relationship between talent management practices and organization commitment is measured by this examination. Further, mediating role of employee engagement was likewise examined. The technique of Taro Yamane was utilized to choose the sample size of 341 employees selected as managers, officials and Sr officials. Recently approved valid adopted instruments were utilized for the measurements. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for TM exercises (.956), organization commitment (.880), and employee's engagement (.876) showed solid survey reliability. The discoveries showed significant positive connections between TM rehearses and organization responsibility, while employee's engagement was partially essentially intervened in the connection between TM rehearses and organization commitment. Subsequently, if TM rehearses are viably taken care of and composed adequately, it will influence the enhancement of organization commitment and employees engagement among various classifications of employees.

Introduction

This examination was done in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan Private Banking Sector utilizing cross-sectional, quantitative research design plan & survey research methodology. The direct relationship between talent management practices and organization commitment is measured by this examination. Further, mediating role of employee engagement was likewise examined. The technique of Taro Yamane was utilized to choose the sample size of 341 employees selected as managers, officials and Sr officials. Recently approved valid adopted instruments were utilized for the measurements. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for TM exercises (.956), organization commitment (.880), and employee's engagement (.876) showed solid survey reliability. The discoveries showed significant positive connections between TM rehearses and organization responsibility, while employee's engagement was partially essentially intervened in the connection between TM rehearses and organization commitment. Subsequently, if TM rehearses are viably taken care of and composed adequately, it will influence the enhancement of organization commitment and employees engagement among various classifications of employees.

TM is a very important topic in terms of research in academia and in many organizations. Professional and scholarly awareness in TM field began from Mckinsey and his associates in 1998 from a well-known manuscript "The War for Talent" and uniquely lately it has been given extraordinary consideration from scholastics and HR specialists (Meyers *et al*; 2020). Similarly, Mathew (2015) expressed that in the present tough business climate of going worldwide and rivalry getting extreme, associations have mounting strain to perform better than anyone might have expected. Throughout the long term, procurement and propagation of talent has become a critical device in speeding up seriousness and upgrading organizational capacities to react to showcase changes wherein workers' abilities and personalities are fittingly sent to advance execution. Besides, recognizing and creating executives who have initiative potential, similar to each and every other imperative key capacity, is a requesting interaction. Associations today are stood up to by cultural advancements like globalization, mechanical upgrades, segment changes and expanding worldwide rivalry. These developments cause deficiency of laborers as well as hazard losing talented employees.

Gallardo *et al.* (2020) suggested a part from growing popularity of talent management it is required actually more understanding on what occurs practically in the work place, which will help with offering more significant investigation. Like, current practices and philosophy that work in a startup deciding to draw in, select, train, and

hold key representatives are not really reasonable in a huge worldwide industry (Collings *et al.*, 2019). So, if companies embraced viable talent management practices, it will not only upgraded organizational commitment but also will develop their personnel (Gümüş *et al.*, 2013).

Also, nowadays a basic test for affiliations is sustaining of organization commitment in view of critical levels of occupation vulnerability inside affiliations (Ng and Feldman, 2008). Association responsibility is relied upon to affect any direct which is important to the affiliation and thusly, it has been given mind boggling thought in the OB field (Fu *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, employees engagement is consider as a main key to hold the talent. So, employee engagement filed required further academic investigation (Cartwright and Holmes, 2006; Shuck, Reio Jr, and Rocco, 2011). As indicated by Martel (2003) for high performance, high productivity firms are required to draw attention to engaged in their employees. For workers commitment it is required a lot of consideration for certain activities like execution the executives, strengthening, correspondence, and administrative connections. Accordingly, representative commitment substantially affects worker efficiency and talent retaining (Bhatnagar, 2007).

Significance of the study

There are different research gaps and shortcomings inside the TM literature which are required further reasonable & hypothetical turn of events (Iqbal *et al.*, 2013). So, future exploration needed to look TM with explicit organization outcomes (Gallardo *et al.*, 2013). Besides, firms will be more focusing in on holding future talent, so accordingly there is still need of extra investigation on TM program in Pakistan (Saddozai *et al.*, 2017). So, the current examination tends to these gaps and explored the relationship among different TM activities and organization commitment in the financial area workers of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. In spite of the consideration that has been acquired by talent management, not very many investigations have shown how TM rehearses are connected with the hierarchical commitment particularly inside Pakistan. Information on whether and how TM rehearses are related with hierarchical commitment, and the instruments that may cause such associations with interceding part of employees engagement actually needs explanation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Talent and Talent Management

For the understanding meaning of TM first and foremost it is significant an investigation of the meaning of talent. Various people and organizations have characterized talent in a different way. As per (Michaels *et al.*, 2001) who imagined 'the fight for talent' interestingly. They depict talent as the summation of individual capacity incorporates their capacities, information and abilities and possibilities for additional development. Essentially, Fishman (1998) communicated that ability is the main corporate resource refined experts who are imaginatively capable, operationally amazing and comprehensive scholarly. This comprehensively definition compares with (Phillips and Roper, 2009), who considered ability is most significant resources for the association.

As per Blass (2007), TM can be defined as the extra administration, procedure and openings that are made accessible to individuals in the association who are viewed as talented. Ventures, for example, counseling and other expert administrations stand or fall by individuals they enlist and hold, and need a strong ability base to guarantee a bigger pool of "high possibilities" inside their associations than different enterprises. In this sense, it is significant that any ability the executive's framework is incorporated across all parts of human resource management. There are clear inter-dependencies amongst TM and enrollment, advancement, diversity, maintenance and succession planning management (Blass and April, 2008). Collings and Mellahi (2009), characterized TM program as a systematic procedure which perceived higher levels positions to support association's diversely in competitive advantages. Subsequently, TM as the proficient interest, commitment, re-pressure, distinguishing proof, and position of those people with extraordinary potential and who for an association are viewed as especially significant.

While, others like, (Adamsky, 2003) reflected talent management is simply fresh mark for human resource management. They perceived talent management as "old wine in another container" Interestingly, others measured TM is a development type of HRM. They considered talent management another methodology of overseeing capable representatives and adjusting them to accomplished association objectives and destinations (Iles *et al.*, 2010).

Talent Management Practices

TM Practices incorporates various sorts of activities that associations are receiving to gets and holds exceptionally proficient and master representatives. Forthright and Taylor (2004), expressed TM rehearses have been created and carried out in numerous associations because of numerous alterations and difficulties in the

working environment like industrialized unrest, globalization, worker's organizations and outsourcing. As the battle for ability is more pervasive in 21st century everywhere on the world, consequently, associations are needed to hold, pull in, motivate, and create skilled representatives to reaction these challenges.

As indicated by Lyria *et al.* (2017), that primary components of TM rehearses are ability maintenance, ability fascination, profession the board, learning and advancement and, every one of these TM activities would be adequately coordinated & carried out in such a manner to achieve vital requirements of the industry. While, Kaliannan *et al.* (2016) infers that primary components of talent management rehearses are staffing and enlistment, maintenance of staff, preparing & development, appreciations and advantages that are compelling in the exhibition of association. This examination focused in on key talent management featured as identified by various investigations and consider TM rehearses like talent procedure, career management, learning and improvement, capability development, retention policies, total compensation, performance management & leadership and high potential development.

Organization Commitment

In the preceding few decades, organization responsibility acquired gigantic thought from experts and considered organization commitment as ordinarily communicated wonders in organization behavior field. Different individuals, and organizations have portrayed organizational responsibility in a different manner. Usually, organizational responsibility described by (Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1979) as: (a) a solid conviction and acknowledgment of destinations and estimations of the affiliation's (b) status to put on critical battle for the association and (c) a certifiable wish to proceed with hierarchical alliance. Whereas, Meyer *et al.* (2006) communicated that the psychological relationship among the delegate and the affiliation is truly association responsibility. Moreover, Meyer and Allen (1991), examined diverse dimensions of organization commitment as a mental state & expressed three broad ideas for hierarchical responsibility. Three various sorts of organization commitment an representative having: (1) Affective responsibility; if its solid the worker will remain to the association since he has/her passionate connection with it; (2) Continuance Commitment; worker stay to their association since he should accept cost in the event that he left it; and (3) Normative responsibility; representatives accept it as a duty to stay with their association. It shows the person's mental connection and power of sensation of their duties towards the vision and mission of their association.

Employee Engagement

In recent years, employee engagement among different firms has received significant attention and has become the focus of several narrative reviews (Ram & Prabhakar, 2011; W. Schaufeli & Salanova, 2007). Employee's engagement has been defined in a different way by different organizations and individuals. Like, Kahn (1990) describes personal engagement as "the harnessing of the self of corporate participants to their work roles; in engagement, individuals physically, cognitively, and emotionally appoint and designate themselves throughout role performances. Richman (2006) expressed that the dedication of employees is focused on the commitment of employees to their physical and mental work to complete the vision, task, and objectives of the company. Most concepts of employee involvement therefore centered on employee emotional and rational affiliation with his or her institution.

Employee's engagement is a point of view about a group's satisfaction with, fulfillment in and obligation with his/her work and affiliation. It is a positive affiliation which one has with his work. It is the level to which workers center around something in their affiliation and for how long they will stay in their firms due to that duty (Corporate Leadership Council, 2004). It is assessed by how much workers have a vibe of satisfaction and energetic conspiracy for business accomplishment. It brings improvement, assembles productivity and helps in holding delegates (Taylor, 2011). Laborer responsibility isn't just about acceptable feelings and practices of agents during work. It can moreover be implied by "affiliation citizenship lead, obligation and high commitment work practices." It is used as a procedure to get the staff work all the more genuinely. There are three sorts of responsibility: (a) Intellectual responsibility; how much agents are up to speed in their work and figure they can improve ways; (b) Affective Engagement; degree to which people have a positive outlook on their work and affiliation; and (c) Social Engagement; where delegates talk about their work experiences and upgrades they have made in work with their get-together of individuals (Purcell, 2010).

Theoretical Framework

The hypothetical framework for the research derived from existing theories, such as the theory of human capital developed by Becker *et al.* (2009) & theory of social exchange developed by Blau (1964) and Meyer (1991) organization commitment model as mentioned in Figure-1.

Figure.1

Methodology

Measurement

For the measurement items, earlier validated constructs were used. To measure the measurement and structural model for data analysis, version 3.0 of the Smart PLS was used.

Reliability and Validity

Coefficient estimation of Cronbach's alpha for TM rehearses (.956), employee's engagement (.876), and organization commitment (.880) demonstrated high consistency of surveys. Likewise, Table 1 displays that composite reliability is over the estimation of 0.7 edge as recommended by (Hair *et al.*, 2011) that affirmed interior consistency dependability.

Convergent validity

The average variance extracted values for every one of the three constructs are over the estimation of (0.5) edge as suggested by (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Hair *et al.*, 2011) thus accordingly set up convergent legitimacy as shown in Table-1.

Table-1 Reliability scores

Construct	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Employee engagement	0.510	0.876	0.904
Organizational Commitment	0.548	0.880	0.909
Talent Management practices	0.501	0.956	0.960

Discriminant validity

For confirming discriminant validity the Fornell-Larcker Criterion general guidelines are satisfied as shown in table-2.

Table-2: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Employee engagement	Organizational commitment	TM practices
Employee engagement	0.714		
Organization Commitment	0.571	0.714	
TM practices	0.506	0.585	0.708

Structural Model

Underlying model discoveries appeared in Table-3 & Figure-2. The result shows that talent management practices has a positive and significant influence on organization commitment at (beta=0.289, t-value=5.714 & p-value<0.000). Furthermore, talent management practices has a positive and significant influence on employees engagement at (beta=0.506, t-value=9.596 & p-value<0.000). Similarly, there is significant and positive relationship amongst employee’s engagement and organization commitment at (beta=0.571, t-value=11.964 and p-value<0.000). Besides, R2 value for reliant variable (OC) 0.327 implies absolute consolidate impact of all independent variables be able to affect 32% change in organization commitment. Furthermore, R2 for employee’s engagement was 0.256 that shows employees engagement can cause 25% variance.

Table 3: : Structural Model Results

	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
TM practices > OC	0.289	0.045	5.714	0.000	Supported
TM practices > EE	0.506	0.053	9.596	0.000	Supported
EE > OC	0.571	0.048	11.964	0.000	Supported

Fig-2 Structure Model

Mediation

Table 4 displays employees engagement intervene relationship among TM rehearses and organization commitment. The t esteem is above 1.99 (t= 6.058, p < 0.000) that clarify EE as significant mediating variable.

Table-4

	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
TM practices > EE > OC	0.289	0.056	6.058	0.000	Supported

Discussion

Hypotheses 1: There is a significant positive connection between talent management practices & organization commitment.

Outcomes showed significant positive relationship amongst talent management activities & organization commitment. These outcomes upheld investigation of (Gümüş *et al.*, 2013; Nobarieidishe *et al.*, 2014; Collings and Mellahi, 2009; Friday and Sunday, 2019). Thus, in case associations need to increment organization commitment level amongst their worker, they ought to give possible talent management rehearses.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant positive connection between talent management practices & employees engagement.

Outcomes showed significant positive connotation among TM activities & job satisfaction. Outcomes upheld research of (Bhatnagar, 2007; Srivastava and Bhatnagar, 2008; O'Connor and Crowley-Henry, 2019). Therefore, if associations need to increment job satisfaction level amongst their workers, they ought to provide possible TM practices.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant positive association amongst employee's engagement & organization commitment

Results showed significant positive connection among employees engagement & organization commitment. These outcomes upheld investigation of (Albdour and Altarawneh, 2014; W. Kim *et al.*, 2017; Chordiya, Sabharwal, & Goodman, 2017). Thus, if associations need to increment organization commitment level amongst their worker, they ought to give possible TM practices.

Hypothesis 4: Employees engagement mediate association among talent management practices & organization commitment

Results showed that employee's engagement found interceding variable in the relationship amongst talent management activities & organization commitment. Though, a lack of empirical studies occurs on examining mediating part of employee's engagement amongst TM activities & organization commitment. Like, study of (Alrowwad *et al.*, 2018) affirmed that employee's engagement fully interceding in the relationship amongst talent management & organization performance. Besides, (Jehangir & Khan, 2018) result showed that worker commitment intervenes the connection between TM and representative inventiveness. Thus, this is noteworthy contribution to the current TM literature.

Conclusion

Main motivation behind this study was to investigate direct link amongst TM practices and organization commitment. Further, it was also discussed the mediating role of employees engagement between TM activities and organization commitment. A cross-sectional, quantitative and survey analysis approach carried out *in this study directed* in the private banking area of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan. Overall result showed an important positive link amongst TM activities & organization commitment. In addition, this investigation affirmed an intermediate position of *employee's engagement* amongst TM activities & organization commitment.

Theoretical implication

This examination contributes to TM activities, organizational commitment & employee's engagement literature by giving verification with regards to banking area in Pakistan. This examination has made certain hypothetical contribution and give critical commitment to the current hypotheses (like the hypothesis of social exchange, and the hypothesis of human capital) and recommended that these speculations can be utilized to the TM activities using different variables.

Practical implications

Findings of this research have practical implications for understanding the status & relationship of talent management activities, organizational commitment & employee engagement for individuals and managers. Administrations can also increase organizational commitment & employee engagement if TM strategies are successfully handled and implemented effectively in their firms.

Recommendations for future research

Upcoming examinations ought to be done based on a longitudinal premise that covers progressions in the factors over the period of time. To see the elements of these factors at public and worldwide levels, this examination ought to likewise be completed at national levels. *Other factors may also be evaluated as mediating factors. In addition, for potential research, the researcher recommends mixed method study for future study.*

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